

Paper 8

**CONCERNS AND PERSPECTIVES OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN
NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020**

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ABSTRACT

The new National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has generated a lot of ambition, expectations and eagerness among people, especially students. The students are the prime stakeholders in the education system as stated by the document. This statement implies that the NEP looks at the students not as ‘citizens of tomorrow’ but as ‘citizens of today’ who are an equal stakeholder in the policies related to the development of the country. Children in rural areas continue to suffer from lack of infrastructure, inadequate staff, etc and are deprived of quality education because of such reasons. Of the many themes that have captured attention, the main idea being inclusion and equity. This encompasses a wide category of children belonging to marginalised groups, minorities, LGBT groups, socially disadvantaged sections, Differently abled children etc. Education must also be a facilitator for achieving social justice and equality where inclusive education and equity in education is so critical that every citizen of the country has the opportunity to dream, thrive and contribute to the nation.

The author has written an article with the main objective of analysing the concerns and perspectives of Inclusive education. The background of the study includes a preview of previous policies concerning inclusiveness followed by current research done by various modes in relevance to inclusive education. The challenges have been highlighted by the author pointing out the key recommendations for fostering inclusive education. The article is concluded with implications towards the implementation of NEP 20 in relevance to inclusiveness and equity.

Keywords: National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, Inclusive Education, marginalised groups, minorities, LGBT groups, socially disadvantaged sections, Differently abled children.

Introduction

The launch of the much awaited National Education Policy (NEP) which came about an excruciating wait of over three decades has been one of the biggest highlights of this year. The

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theme of inclusion and equity have captured public attention from the many ideas put across in the Policy. The idea of Inclusive Education has often revolved around making education accessible and available for all, especially for children from marginalized milieus among all the education policies throughout the years. The concept started gaining currency in India post the 1990s and was borrowed from recognized international settings (mainly through international intergovernmental organizations like UNESCO, World Bank etc.). India, though, still lacks a well recognized ‘working definition’ and shared understanding of ‘Inclusive Education’ as the initial keystone of inclusive education was limited to ‘special education’ or inclusion of children with disability, which has seen some expansion in the past few years.

Inclusive education is seen as taking “a holistic approach to education reform and thus changing the way the educational system tackles exclusion” according to some well-accepted international definitions (from a policy perspective) view. Literature ensures the “presence, participation and achievement of all students” and their diversities and views “inclusion as a process which is concerned with the identification and removal of barriers” of education. Students having vulnerable identities are at a greater risk of marginalization and exclusion from education and thus need greater attention than others.

The Policy also suggests measures to improve equity in education in three key policy domains: the design of education systems, practices both in and out of school and resourcing. In order to reduce school failure and dropout rates, the policy proposes measures which would help avoid the large social costs of marginalised adults with few basic skills. As the Policy makes new changes, governments are required to measure success in improving equity, performance and dropout rates. The author has tried to bring out the prominence of Inclusive Education in relevance to NEP 20 by highlighting the reviews of past and current studies, recommendations and key challenges followed by exploring the applications of Inclusive education under broader social concepts.

Objective: To analyse the National Educational Policy 2020 with relevance to Inclusive Education

Background of the Study

Review of Previous Policies- NPE 1968, NPE 1986 and NPE 1992 with regard to Inclusive Education

The Government of India formulated the National Policy on Education (NPE) to promote education among the people of India. **The NPE 1968** was broadcasted under the leadership of

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Prime Minister Indira Gandhi which focused mainly on ‘Radical Restructuring’. This had to involve a transformation of the system to relate more closely to the life of people, a continuous effort to expand educational opportunity, a sustained and intense effort to raise the quality of education at all stages, an emphasis of development of science and technology and thus help in character building. Strenuous efforts were made to equalise the principle of Educational Opportunity which included provision of educational facilities to rural, urban and backward areas and girls’ education, promotion of cohesion and national integration of the common school system and expansion of educational facilities for differently abled children and devising programmes for their integration in regular schools.

Under the Government of Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi, the **NPE 1986** was framed on ‘Special emphasis on removal of disparities and to equalise educational opportunity’. The main objective was to provide equivalent educational opportunities to all including women, SC, STs through scholarships, incentives, promotion of adult education and providing housing and services.

The **NPE 1992** was adopted by P.V Narasimha Rao and recognised as ‘Common Minimum Programme’. This Policy provided a comprehensive action plan for the inclusion of education for SC, ST, handicapped, Women Education, Education for Tribes, Adults and Minorities.

Highlights of NEP 20 Research Analyses by various Modes

In an article published in Times of India about ‘NEP 20: Making Education more Inclusive’ by Anuja (2020) has expressed about the structural change in the education system with the aim of equity and inclusion ensuring the wide range of educational opportunities and designing a curriculum to avoid segregation and isolation of ethnic and linguistic minorities, those with disabilities and also those who are at the risk of educational exclusion facing learning difficulties due to language barriers.

A Critique done by Niranjana Sahoo (2020) on ‘Equitable and Inclusive Vision on NEP 20’ mentions about how NEP 2020 attempts to address the growing inequality and inequity plaguing country’s education system today. The author has described key challenges on inclusive education and records that the NEP has to head on with the recognition of dropout rates among socio-economic strata and weaker minorities as well as recognition of barriers that lead to incompetent resource allocations such as small school campuses and causes for lesser participation of the girl child in rural areas,.

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Research conducted by Sarkar, Tanushree (2020) on ‘Education and Disabilities’ examines the relationship between education policy and teacher practices for inclusive education in India. The study is concluded with an analysis of implications of the NEP for children with disabilities around four key aspects: (i) school choice, (ii) teacher and special educators, (iii) assessments and curricula, and (iv) terminology of inclusion and disability.

An article published by the DailyHunt News App lays special emphasis on moving towards Inclusive and equitable education. The article stresses on the transformational role taken by the NEP 20 in determining the prospects of sustainable educational opportunities and its implementation by considering equal education to all masses.

Thematic paper written by Dam, Tinanjali (2020) highlights about the formation of an inclusive education policy that requires research and a scientific study of each aspect mentioned in it. The paper is concluded by framing research questions about analysing the problems of all types of students especially those belonging from marginalised sections.

Thus from the above related literature it can be concluded that the NEP aims to facilitate an inclusive, participatory and holistic approach and ensure equity and inclusion in and through education by addressing all forms of exclusion and marginalization, disparity, vulnerability and inequality in education access, participation, retention and completion and in learning outcomes.

Challenges of NEP 20 with regard to Inclusive Education

Key Recommendations for fostering Inclusive Education with significance to NEP 2020

- **Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs)**

With its objectives on creating inclusivity, the NEP 2020 clubbed the inadequately represented groups such as gender identities, socio-cultural identities, geographical identities, disabilities, and socio-economic conditions to create a new social group called SEDGs to specially address the educational needs around these groups. The NEP 2020 recommends a series of policies and schemes such as targeted scholarships, conditional cash transfers to incentivize parents to send their children to school, providing bicycles for transport that have worked in the past to increase enrolment and by recognising their special needs, to create more representation.

Certain challenges to this broad categorization are:

The policy does not prescribe the need for reservations and does not recognize caste as a

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historical inhibitor. Similarly, there is no recognition of the multiple structural inhibitors that plague these communities from succeeding in educational institutions because of the constant discrimination that they face from multiple sources. Importantly, the need for giving consent is considered minimal to give equal representation. The policy does not include recognition of caste inclusion and affirmative action for teacher appointments.

- **Recognition of gendered identities**

The NEP 2020 recognises that female and transgender individuals across all the groups and socio-economic categories are the worst affected people and therefore schemes of giving out bicycles to form cycling groups and creating walking groups to schools to include community participation and make safety ways for these vulnerable students needs to be implemented.

Further, the new policy proposes the creation of a ‘Gender-Inclusion Fund’ to create better educational spaces for women and transgender individuals. The fund will be accessible to states to create systems that will help the inclusion of these students with the initiation of provisions of sanitation, conditional cash transfers, bicycle distribution schemes, etc. Additionally, states will be enabled funds to support and scale up effective community-based interventions that address local context-specific barriers to female and transgenders’ access to and participation in education. In this regard, to provide better boarding facilities for students to tackle geographical barriers to education the policy recommends establishment of Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalayas.

The NEP has not paid attention in addressing core issues of inclusivity and conversations that are missing in the existing schooling systems. Historically, there are several types of issues pertaining to discrimination based on sexual identification and orientation of individuals and specific discrimination that transgender individuals’ face in workspaces.

A recent CBSE press release illustrates the judicial abolishment of Article 377, as per, there were 1,889,878 candidates in class 10 and 1,206,893 candidates in class 12. Among the students who registered for class 10 exam, 7,88,195 were girls, 11,01,664 were boys, only 19 were transgender persons. For class 12, as many as 5,22,819 were girls, 6,84,068 were boys, and six were transgender persons.

A large indication of numerical disparity shows that the barriers faced by transgender individuals are disproportionately high. The new policy does not outline how it plans to increase enrollment for these students, nor does it suggest ways to solve discrimination that

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these individuals face as they enter educational institutions that lead to disproportionately exacerbated dropout rates.

- **Recognition of individuals with special needs**

The policy recognizes the differently abled children and believes in incorporating them into the mainstream education systems and is in par with the objectives of The Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act 2016.

The policy also aims to recruit special educators in all school complexes to make sure that teaching is more inclusive and the school is knowledgeable about the needs of children. An option of homeschooling would be provided with skilled homeschooling educators so that students can still learn and acquire the best educational facilities especially for those with benchmark disabilities

Further, teachers will be trained to identify learning disabilities in children at an early stage and help children with learning disabilities succeed in education and take care of their mental health. To create equitable systems of assessment for children with learning disabilities the National Assessment Centre, PARAKH will be formulated and alternate models for schooling are proposed to advance this objective.

The challenge lies in where the NEP fails to recognize the fact that not only most teachers are poorly trained for such special assignments, but most of the schools in India have no sufficient manpower to train the special children. The policy does not justify the planning of creating alternative homeschooling mechanisms that are accessible to individuals.

The new policy fails to specify a roadmap of explaining reasons for making education accessible to these individuals. It doesnot prescribe or modify the curriculum to be adopted for children with learning disabilities so as to avoid them from being excluded in the extremely competitive environments

- **Creation of Special Educational Zones**

One of the main recommendations of the NEP is the proposal to set up Special Educational Zones (SEZs) in regions with significant population belonging to Socio Economically Disadvantaged Groups and in those aspirational districts with the key purpose to spread education in the remotest and farthest places in India. This will be done by pooling in extra resources with the alignment of multiple schemes and programmes of Centre and states with the intent of transforming these backward regions.

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With the idea of transforming educational access in inaccessible areas of the country (such as urban areas with substantial minority population), the policy has not specified what is the criterion to be followed for these zones to distinguish them from urban and rural landscapes. The policy has no clear indicator of what would be the determining factors to make education accessible to these places.

Challenges for Equity in Education in regard to NEP 20

The two dimensions for Equity in education consist of: (1) fairness, which basically means there should not be any obstacle to achieving educational potential in terms of personal and social circumstances –gender, socio-economic status or ethnic origin. (2) Inclusion, in other words ensuring a basic minimum standard of education for all –everyone should be able to read, write and do simple arithmetic.

Three key policy areas that can affect equity in education: the design of education systems, practices in and out of school, and how resources are allocated. The Organisation for Economic and Social Development (OECD) has recommended steps that governments can take in these three areas which would reduce school failure and dropout rates, make society fairer and avoid the large social costs of marginalised adults with few basic skills.

Ways to improve the Design of the Educational System

Equity is affected by the basic structure of education system. Evidence from studies of secondary and primary schools suggests that sorting students based on attainment can increase inequalities and inequities, particularly if it takes place early in the education process. Overall results are weakened by early sorting. This concludes as early tracking and streaming need to be justified in terms of proven benefits; and school systems using early tracking should postpone it to a later stage to reduce inequities and improve outcomes. This can be done through,

- Limiting early tracking and streaming and postpone academic selection
- School choice management to contain the risks to equity
- Provision of attractive alternatives and prevent dropouts in upper secondary education.

Ways to improve Practices in and outside the classroom

Student learning benefits from an effective school-home relationship, but weak support at home can hold back children from deprived backgrounds. a key challenge is the effective provision for migrants and minorities in the education system. The Practices include,

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- Identification and provision of systematic help to those who fall behind at school and reduce year repetition
- Strengthening the links between school and home to help disadvantaged parents help their children to learn.
- Responding to diversity and provide for the successful inclusion of migrants and minorities within mainstream education.

Ways to improving Resources for Equity in Education

Education systems need to provide strong education for all, giving priority to early childhood provision and basic schooling. Public provision of education can foster equity if it counterbalances poor home circumstances at the outset of children’s lives. But it may increase inequity if it offers a common resource that is primarily claimed by those least in need of it. Resourcing can be done by,

- Provision of strong education for all, giving priority to early childhood provision and basic schooling.
- Providing direct resources to the students with the greatest needs.
- Setting concrete targets for more equity, particularly related to low school attainment and dropouts.

Implications towards the implementation of NEP 20 in relevance of Equity and Inclusive Education

• Researches done on Policies on Inclusive Education

Clear, comprehensive policies on inclusive education related to teacher education need to be aligned with broader inclusive education policy objectives, with a need to address issues specific to inequalities in the recruitment of student teachers and teacher educators (e.g. disproportionately low number of women, people from ethnic/linguistic minority backgrounds, indigenous peoples, people from remote areas, and people with disabilities); support for promoting inclusive teaching and learning methodologies and continuous formative and authentic assessment; collaborative working between peers of teacher educators, student teachers, and between teacher education institutions and schools/school communities; and capacity to support diverse learners and teach inclusively, including opportunities for in-service professional development.

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- **coordination and collaboration within and between government ministries**

The potential for a unified approach to addressing the cross-cutting issues that are not specifically education related, such as poverty, disability, migration, poor health, the exclusion of ethnic minorities, etc. is lessened by a lack of or weak collaboration between ministries of education and other governmental ministries (e.g. ministries that deal with health, social welfare, orphans, migrant workers, persons with disabilities, women, etc.)

Greater efforts should be made towards communication and coordination for inclusive education among government ministries, teacher education institutions and non-governmental/inter-governmental organizations.

- **supporting the participation of local communities in education in schools**

The policies need to recognize the active participation of local communities e.g. parents/families, community and religious groups, who can successfully support the education for all learners. Marginalized people and communities (e.g. people living in poverty, people with disabilities, ethnic and linguistic minorities, indigenous peoples, migrant workers, people living in remote areas, women, etc.) are often excluded from, or underrepresented within teacher education institutions, and policies need to support members of such groups entering the teaching profession that are often non-existent, weak, and/or poorly implemented

- **Schools can be held accountable for building stronger links with their communities**

Policies can also play a role in supporting better relationships between local communities and teacher education institutions. This can be done through supporting student teachers to do practicum work in local schools; volunteer services in local schools; support in-service teachers in local schools to receive additional training and qualifications from teacher education institutions; inviting in-service teachers and school management staff in local schools to give guest lectures or share their knowledge and skills in pre-service teacher education institutions.

- **Implementing policies to support students from marginalized groups, migrants, ethnic, racial and minority communities**

Efforts need to be done to enhance the diversity of students belonging to different races and culture. Educational institutions in conjunction with district level education offices can work with organizations that support people with disabilities and with ethnic minority communities to encourage and support them to receive education.

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Conclusion

The challenges faced by gendered categories, minorities and children with special needs has been recognised by NEP 2020. It has also proposed a series of laudable steps including education SEZs to address the structural challenges of education in inaccessible regions. Yet, the new policy errs on multiple fronts where it has lacked to consider many other historic categories. Similarly, its silence on confirmatory action for certain categories can pave way into multiple challenges at the time of implementation.

India has always placed education at the centre of its development agenda and with bridging the gender, social, regional gaps with community participation it will raise the spirits towards equal opportunities to all ensuring equity in this policy. It is going to be the beautiful blend of both ancient and modern knowledge system which not only inculcates one to acquire knowledge but also helps in integrating Indian culture and ethos.

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